

Novel Fronthaul Control Method to Address the Fronthaul/Air Interface Tradeoff

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Abstract—In 5th Generation (5G) virtualized Radio Access Networks (vRAN), where the protocol stack is split across three different elements (Radio Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU), and Centralized Unit (CU)), and data is transmitted across the transport network (fronthaul (FH) and midhaul) between these units, the capacity of the fronthaul pipe can become a limiting factor for packet transmission. To address this challenge, state-of-the-art approaches have introduced several fronthaul control methods, designed to limit the sending rate, to ensure that it does not exceed the available capacity. However, it is important to avoid potential conflicts between the decisions of such fronthaul control methods and those of the Medium Access Control (MAC) scheduling schemes, as they might impact one another. In this context, we provide a thorough analysis of the trade-off between the fronthaul and the air interface limitations and we propose a new FH Control method to limit packet transmissions without altering the decisions made by the MAC scheduler. An extensive simulation campaign in a 3GPP defined scenario with Virtual Reality (VR) and Cloud Gaming (CG) services is conducted, for air-limited and air/fronthaul capacity-limited conditions. The results demonstrate that the proposed fronthaul control method efficiently coordinates the MAC scheduler decisions with the constraints imposed by the fronthaul capacity.

Index Terms—transport network, fronthaul, virtualized RAN, functional splits.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 5th Generation (5G) virtualized Radio Access Network (vRAN) represents a significant evolution in the mobile network's architecture. Unlike more traditional networks, which employ monolithic hardware configurations, vRAN leverages virtualization, moving towards a software-based architecture that fosters flexibility and scalability. vRAN architecture divides the 5G protocol stack into three geographically distributed network units—the Radio Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU), and Centralized Unit (CU)—which are interconnected via transport networks known as fronthaul and midhaul, respectively. This division enables functional splitting, where different layers of the protocol stack are instantiated at different network units, allowing optimal Radio Access Network (RAN) configurations, tailored to specific scenarios. Particularly, the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has defined functional split option 2 for the CU/DU separation [1]. In this configuration, the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) layer is implemented at the CU, while the Radio Link Control (RLC) and the lower layers are handled by the DU. Additionally, Open RAN (O-RAN) Alliance has defined the

RU entity, specifying the split option 7.2x for the DU and RU division [2]. In this split, high-PHY functions and the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer are implemented at the DU, centralizing MAC layer decisions, while low-PHY functions and Radio Frequency (RF) processing are managed by the RU (see Figure 1).

When the protocol stack is split, the transport network (fronthaul and midhaul) plays a crucial role, as data and control traffic must be transmitted across it. To ensure appropriate operation, the transport network must meet specific latency and capacity requirements, which are determined by the chosen functional split [1]. Although the same transport network can handle traffic from multiple users, its capacity is inherently limited. Therefore, it is essential to take into account the transmitted data across the transport network, i.e. the throughput, to avoid exceeding the maximum available capacity and so ensure appropriate system performance. To address this, [3] proposes Fronthaul (FH)-aware¹ control methods, including baseline and optimized FH-aware scheduling mechanisms, focused on restricting fronthaul downlink traffic so that the transmitted data fits within the available fronthaul capacity.

In addition to fronthaul limitations, for an optimal network operation, the constraints of the air interface must be also considered. The MAC scheduling scheme takes into account the air interface constraints when allocating resources for each User Equipment (UE). To tackle this, various scheduling policies can be applied, such as the well-known and legacy Round Robin (RR), which fosters an equal distribution of resources to the users; and Proportional Fairness (PF), which ensures fairness in terms of accumulated rate to all users. To account for Quality of Service (QoS) parameters, [4] proposed a new QoS scheduler, which is a modified PF version that additionally includes the Packet Delay Budget (PDB), the Head-of-Line (HOL) delay, and the priority of the various QoS flows. Recently, we introduced in [5] a Drift Plus Penalty (DPP) scheduler, which exploits the Lyapunov control theory and is designed to stabilize the transmission queues in order to meet the Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (GFBR) requirements when the air interface is saturated.

¹Since the split option 7.2x has larger throughput requirements on the transport network than functional split option 2, the capacity requirements for the FH are more stringent than for the midhaul. Therefore, this article focuses on the FH, and from now on, we will refer to the transport network as the FH network.

However, if FH and air constraints are managed independently, conflicts may arise between the MAC scheduling schemes and the fronthaul control methods, potentially hindering network performance. Therefore, if the MAC scheduler is implemented at the CU or the DU (as in the O-RAN architecture), it needs to consider both limitations: air interface and transport network.

Going beyond alternative solutions that address the MAC scheduling and fronthaul control separately, in this work we jointly manage both air and fronthaul resource constraints. Towards that purpose, we design and implement a new fronthaul control method that adjusts the MAC scheduler's resource allocation, considering the maximum capacity that can be transmitted over the FH, while still aligning with the MAC scheduler's behavior and air resource management. Without loss of generality, we focus on the downlink case. To evaluate the new fronthaul control method, we have adopted the 5G-LENA simulator, which implements 5G New Radio (NR) protocols in the ns-3 framework. In our evaluation, we use a 3GPP-defined scenario [6] that includes Virtual Reality (VR) and Cloud Gaming (CG) traffic types, each of them with different requirements. We compare the proposed fronthaul control method with state-of-the-art solutions [3], assessing their performance with various MAC schedulers. Specifically, we test the widely adopted PF and QoS scheduling schemes implemented in 5G-LENA, along with the DPP scheduler from our previous work [5]. To assess potential conflicts that may arise between fronthaul control methods and MAC scheduler decisions, we have selected a scenario where air resources are not a limiting factor, as well as a scenario where air resources are limited. Additionally, we have considered various fronthaul capacities, ranging from non-restrictive to highly restrictive configurations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the PF, QoS and DPP scheduling schemes as well as the state-of-the-art fronthaul control methods. Then, Section III introduces the new fronthaul control method proposed in this work. Afterward, Sections IV and V depict the evaluation scenario and discuss the obtained results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

Fig. 1. 5G vRAN architecture, with O-RAN configuration.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a system with one gNB and N users (UE_i with $i = 1, \dots, N$) distributed across a cell. The gNB follows the O-RAN architecture, i.e., it separates CU and

DU using split option 2, and DU and RU with split option 7.2x, leading to an intra-PHY split. As stated before, we focus on split option 7.2x (Figure 1) where the FH pipe capacity is defined by C^{FH} . In this split, most of the physical layer processing, including coding, modulation, layer and resource element mapping occurs at the DU, along with the MAC layer centralization, which directly impact the throughput transmitted over the fronthaul [7]. Specifically, the allocation of radio resources is determined by the MAC scheduling scheme and the multiple access scheme. A radio resource is defined as a combination of a Resource Block (RB) in the frequency domain and an Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM) symbol in the time domain. The multiple access scheme dictates how radio resources are divided and which ones can be allocated, i.e. RBs in case of Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) and OFDM symbols in case of Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA). On the other hand, the scheduling scheme determines to which user the resources are assigned. Consequently, the more radio resources allocated for data transmission, the more data will be sent through the FH.

The calculation of the throughput required on the FH depends on the type of data exchanged between DU and RU, and it varies based on the functional split [1]. For functional split option 7.2x, the resource element mapping is performed at the DU, and the throughput is therefore calculated considering all radio resources assigned to active users within a slot with t^{slot} duration. The number of resources assigned to a UE in a slot are represented by $(N_i^{RB} \cdot N_i^{\text{sym}})$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, being N_i^{RB} the number of radio resources in an OFDM symbol. N_i^{sym} is the number of OFDM symbols in a segment of the slot defined by the OFDMA scheme with variable Transmission Time Interval (TTI). With this access scheme, the slot is divided into two or more segments in time, each segment being used for a single antenna beam. The number of OFDM symbols in each segment can vary. The UEs access the corresponding segment's radio resources using the OFDMA scheme. This means that one RB for all OFDM symbols within a segment is allocated to the same UE. Additionally, each N_i^{RB} contains 12 subcarriers. W_i represents the bits per sample transmitted and, if modulation compression technique is used, W_i equals the modulation order assigned to the user [3]. N_i^L represents the spatial layers that are used to transmit different data by reusing the same subcarrier and OFDM symbol. Besides, additional MAC information needs to be transmitted to the low-PHY layer, MAC_i^{info} (in bits). According to [8], $MAC_i^{\text{info}}/t^{\text{slot}}$ is 0.7Mbps and 0.120Mbps, in DL and UL, respectively, for split 7.2x. Then, the total transmitted throughput is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Throughput} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(12 \cdot N_i^{\text{sym}} \cdot N_i^{RB} \cdot W_i \cdot N_i^L + MAC_i^{\text{info}})}{t^{\text{slot}}} \quad (1)$$

A. MAC Scheduling Schemes

5G-LENA includes various scheduler implementations, such as RR, PF, and QoS. The objective of RR and PF scheduling schemes is to proportionally distribute the available radio resources among the active UEs. However, PF takes into account the actual bit rate and the average bit rate obtained in previous slots to assign resources proportionally. Unlike other schedulers, the QoS scheduler implemented in the 5G-LENA module is the only one that takes QoS parameters into account. These parameters define the requirements that each traffic type or application must meet for optimal performance. Among other aspects, QoS parameters establish priority through the 5G QoS Identifier (5QI) value and the guarantee data rate via the GFBR. In this context, the QoS scheduler in 5G-LENA assigns resources to UEs based on the priority level defined by the 5QI and PDB [4]. However, this scheduler focuses on traffic priorities, without taking into account the GFBR value that should be met for each application. Therefore, in our previous work, we defined and implemented a new scheduling policy in 5G-LENA called DPP, whose objective is to stabilize the traffic flow, meet the QoS GFBR requirements and minimize the use of radio resources. Depending on the scenario of interest, the importance of each objective can be dynamically configured [5].

B. FH control methods

An important factor in functional splits is the maximum capacity that the fronthaul can support, which is imposed by the mobile network operator's deployment. This capacity may limit the amount of data transmitted between different network units of the vRAN. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this limitation when implementing a functional split. To address this, the work in [3] proposes fronthaul control methods, which aim to restrict the amount of traffic transmitted through the fronthaul to ensure it does not exceed the maximum allowed capacity. Baseline methods, such as Dropping and Postponing, as well as optimized methods (e.g. OptimizeRBs) are proposed. The design of the fronthaul control method depends on the chosen split and it does not necessarily have to be implemented in a specific layer, such as in the MAC layer. In 5G-LENA, Dropping, Postponing, and OptimizeRBs fronthaul control methods are implemented in the DU to ensure the fulfillment of the maximum fronthaul capacity for functional split option 7.2x [3].

Dropping fronthaul control method is implemented at the high-PHY layer. Once the MAC scheduling scheme has assigned radio resources for packet transmission, without considering the FH capacity limitation, the allocated resource information along with the data packet is sent to the PHY layer. The high-PHY layer then calculates whether the packet can be transmitted from the DU to the RU through the FH, or if there is not enough capacity in the FH to transmit the packet. In this case, the packet is dropped; otherwise, it is transmitted over the FH. In the case of Postponing, this verification is performed at the MAC layer after the MAC scheduler allocates radio resources without considering fronthaul capacity limitations. If the allocation exceeds the

available capacity, it is discarded, and the packet is stored at the RLC buffer, allowing to find new radio resources for the packet in subsequent slots and avoiding direct packet drops. Finally, OptimizeRBs fronthaul control method is also implemented at the MAC layer. This modifies the MAC scheduling scheme decisions as it calculates the maximum number of radio resources that can be allocated to each user to maximize the minimum achievable throughput across all active UEs in the current slot. In order to calculate this value, OptimizeRBs fronthaul control method considers the total number of active UEs and the maximum available capacity. Then, the maximum available radio resources for each UE is calculated following equation (2).

$$N_i^{RB} = \frac{C^{FH} \cdot t^{\text{slot}} - \sum_{i=1}^N MAC_i^{\text{info}}}{12 \cdot N_i^{\text{sym}} \cdot N_i^L \cdot W_i}, \forall i \in [1, \dots, N] \quad (2)$$

III. ADJUSTRBs FRONTHAUL CONTROL METHOD

This section introduces a novel fronthaul control method, called AdjustRBs, designed to meet fronthaul capacity requirements without altering the MAC scheduling scheme behavior. AdjustRBs, during the resource allocation process, verifies whether the total resources assigned to a user fit within the fronthaul capacity. This new fronthaul control method operates differently from Postponing and Dropping ones, which first allocate all resources and then check if the allocation fits within the fronthaul capacity. Additionally, it differs from the OptimizeRBs fronthaul control method, as AdjustRBs does not restrict the radio resource availability to each UE in advance. As a result, AdjustRBs incorporates the FH awareness in the MAC scheduling process, while at the same time respects the scheduling decisions.

The operation of the AdjustRBs fronthaul control method along with the MAC scheduler configured with the OFDMA scheme with variable TTI is described in Algorithm 1. First, the scheduling scheme selects the UE_i to which the resources will be allocated (line 3). This UE_i is chosen among all users in group G , which gathers all active UEs in that slot. Upon selecting UE_i , the expected throughput to be transmitted with the addition of this user is calculated (represented by variable aux in Algorithm 1). If this is the first time resources are being allocated to this UE in the corresponding slot (line 5), both the UE's allocated resources and the control data to be transmitted for this user are considered. If, on the other hand, radio resources have already been assigned to this UE, the additional throughput is computed excluding the control data (lines 7 and 8). Then, the total throughput that would be transmitted over the FH in one slot (t^{slot}) is calculated following equation (1), which is represented by $Throughput + aux$ in Algorithm 1. If this throughput exceeds the FH capacity, C^{FH} , the last allocated resources will be discarded, and this UE_i will be removed from group G (lines 10-13 in Algorithm 1). Otherwise, the total throughput value will be updated (line 14) and it will check whether the allocated resources are sufficient for the corresponding UE (line 15). If the resources are sufficient, the UE_i will be removed from group G (lines 15-17 in Algorithm 1). Resource allocation will end when all UEs have radio resources assigned, or when the fronthaul

capacity is fully utilized or no more radio resources are available.

Algorithm 1: AdjustRBs fronthaul control method

Input : C^{FH} , UE_i , W_i , N_i^L , MAC_i^{info} , N_i^{sym} with $i = [1, \dots, N]$

Output: Allocated resources N_i^{RB} with $i = [1, \dots, N]$

- 1 Initialize *Throughput*, aux , $N_i^{RB} = 0$, $G = \{UE_i\}$ with $i = [1, \dots, N]$
- 2 **while** ($G \neq \emptyset$) & (there are available radio resources)
- 3 $UE_i =$ select UE from G based on DPP, QoS, or PF criteria
- 4 $N_i^{RB} = N_i^{RB} + 1$
- 5 **if** $N_i^{RB} = 1$
- 6 $aux = (12 \cdot 1 \cdot N_i^{sym} \cdot W_i \cdot N_i^L + MAC_i^{info}) / t^{slot}$
- 7 **else**
- 8 $aux = 12 \cdot 1 \cdot N_i^{sym} \cdot W_i \cdot N_i^L / t^{slot}$
- 9 **end**
- 10 **if** *Throughput* + $aux > C^{FH}$
- 11 $N_i^{RB} = N_i^{RB} - 1$
- 12 $G = G - \{UE_i\}$
- 13 **else**
- 14 *Throughput* = *Throughput* + aux
- 15 **if** UE_i has sufficient resources allocated
- 16 $G = G - \{UE_i\}$
- 17 **end**
- 18 **end**
- 19 **end**

IV. EVALUATION SCENARIO

We have simulated a 5G network deployed in an indoor scenario, using Bandwidth (BW) of 400MHz and 100MHz, with 30dBm and 24dBm transmission power, respectively, and considering a Sub-Carrier Spacing (SCS) of 120 kHz, following the 3GPP scenario described in [6]. The simulations have been carried out in ns-3 5G-LENA module. In this scenario, 14 UEs are distributed randomly; seven UEs run a VR application ($UE_1^{CG}, \dots, UE_7^{CG}$), while the other seven demand CG traffic ($UE_8^{VR}, \dots, UE_N^{VR}$). The gNB transmits VR and CG packets with probabilistic sizes that follow a truncated Gaussian distribution, as specified in [9, Section 5.3.1]. These packets are transmitted in the downlink direction. The network uses an adaptive Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) following Table 2 in TS 38.214, which includes an MCS up to 256QAM. The 5QI for VR is 89, DGBR_VISUAL_CONTENT_89 (high-priority), while for CG equals 3, GBR_GAMING (medium-priority). The GFBR that these applications must meet to operate effectively is 45Mbps and 30Mbps, respectively [9]. We assume that UEs are in Line of Sight (LoS) conditions with the gNB, which is positioned at the center of the cell. UEs are randomly distributed within the cell, with a random deployment in a circular area of 20m radius around the gNB, so that the distance between the gNB and the UEs is between 0 and 20m [6].

The 5G network simulates a virtualized RAN architecture, and functional split option 7.2x is established between RU and DU. We have evaluated the same scenario with varying capacities in the FH. For a scenario where the FH does not limit packet transmission, we have assumed a capacity of 100Gbps. Additionally, we have tested capacities of 2, 1, 0.7, and 0.5Gbps, to analyze the interaction between schedulers and the fronthaul control methods when the fronthaul capacity is restricted. These capacity values are in line with the rates defined for Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) [10]. Figure 2 shows the scenario considered in the evaluation that we describe in what follows.

Fig. 2. Evaluation scenario.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section compares the performance of AdjustRBs with state-of-the-art fronthaul control methods, as described in Section II (i.e., Dropping, Postponing, OptimizeRBs). The comparison is conducted using PF, QoS, and DPP scheduling schemes. The analysis was performed using the ns-3 5G-LENA module. In the following subsections, we present the end-to-end (E2E) performance evaluation. First, as a benchmark, we analyze the scenario where the FH capacity is not a limiting factor, to analyze the behavior and performance of each of the schedulers. Notice that we study an air-limited scenario since the scheduler functionality is more critical under saturation. Then, we examine the same scenario when the FH capacity becomes more limited, impacting network behavior. Additionally, in the limited FH capacity scenario, we consider two bandwidth conditions: a high resource availability scenario with 400 MHz BW and a constrained air interface scenario with fewer available RBs (air-limited scenario with 100 MHz BW).

A. Benchmark scenario

Figure 3 compares the average E2E throughput obtained by VR and CG applications when using DPP, QoS and PF scheduling schemes with a FH capacity of 100Gbps and a bandwidth of 100MHz. In Figure 3 the system is not constrained by the FH capacity but rather by the available bandwidth in the air interface. As a result, the throughput achieved by each application depends on the scheduling scheme, and it does not depend on the chosen fronthaul control method. Figure 3 shows that DPP and QoS achieve

an average throughput that equals the necessary GFBR for both applications, while PF fails to meet the required GFBR for the VR application. This difference arises because DPP considers the GFBR requirements and aims to stabilize the queues when the system is saturated, whereas PF aims to grant a similar rate to both applications without prioritizing the specific GFBR requirements. Moreover, the QoS scheduler successfully meets the GFBR requirements for both traffic types, even though it prioritizes one type of traffic (in this case, VR) over the other to achieve a higher data rate for the prioritized traffic.

Fig. 3. Average throughput as a function of schedulers and 100Gbps capacity.

B. FH capacity limited scenario

Table I shows the percentage of achieved throughput, compared to the required GFBR for VR and CG. For instance, if the obtained average throughput for VR is 45Mbps, which matches the GFBR for VR, the achieved throughput equals 100%. Furthermore, if the obtained throughput is 30Mbps, the achieved throughput for CG would also be 100%. Table I shows that when the capacity is not highly reduced (2Gbps), both OptimizeRBs and AdjustRBs can achieve very high percentages, with no clear improvement of AdjustRBs over OptimizeRBs, as both are close to the optimal throughput or GFBR. However, the difference between these methods becomes noticeable when the capacity is reduced to 700 or 500Mbps. In such cases, AdjustRBs can assign the desired throughput to each application by following the scheduler's logic, while OptimizeRBs alters this logic and fails to meet the required QoS parameters for the applications. In other words, DPP with AdjustRBs is the combination that better approaches the required GFBR for both applications and all simulated capacities. Additionally, AdjustRBs with the QoS scheduler achieves the highest throughput for the VR case for all evaluated capacities, following the prioritization of VR over CG. In contrast, with OptimizeRBs, as the FH capacity becomes more restrictive, both schedulers tend to achieve similar throughput percentages, as their behavior becomes more aligned, due to the fact that resource allocation is limited by OptimizeRBs. Moreover, with QoS and OptimizeRBs, the scheduling scheme behavior changes to the point that the prioritization of VR no longer exists, and the one that achieves the highest throughput is CG. Table I also shows that when using PF with AdjustRBs, the obtained throughput is significantly lower. This is because PF struggles to deliver the required throughput regardless of the FH capacity, as we have

seen in Figure 3. Therefore, since AdjustRBs does not alter the behavior of the scheduling schemes, the more restrictive the FH capacity is, the lower the throughput will be when the PF scheduler is used, as it tries to provide a data rate to all UEs, increasing the control traffic (MAC_{info}) transmitted over the FH.

TABLE I
% OF OBTAINED THROUGHPUT WITH VR/CG APPLICATIONS AS A FUNCTION OF FH CAPACITY.

Fronthaul control methods	Scheduling Schemes	FH Capacity (Mbps)		
		2000	700	500
AdjustRBs	DPP	99/98.8	83.7/84.5	63.3/55.5
	QoS	99.9/99.1	99.8/44.1	81.5/1
	PF	95.1/98.8	49.2/73.4	30/44.7
OptimizeRBs	DPP	95.5/93.5	26.6/39.6	26.6/39.6
	QoS	93.5/86.7	26.6/39.6	26.6/39.6
	PF	89.7/97.3	26.6/39.6	26.6/39.6

Figure 4 shows the average E2E throughput, comparing different FH control methods across different FH capacities, ranging from 100Gbps (least restrictive) to 500Mbps (most restrictive). For this graph, we selected the DPP scheduler based on the results presented in Table I. In Figure 4.a, the bandwidth is 400 MHz, while in Figure 4.b, it is 100 MHz.

Fig. 4. Average throughput as a function of fronthaul control methods and FH capacities when using DPP scheduler and a BW of a) 400MHz and b) 100MHz.

As seen in Figure 4, the AdjustRBs fronthaul control method consistently achieves equal or better throughput than other methods across all capacities. As the FH capacity becomes more restrictive, the throughput decreases for each application. For capacities up to 1Gbps, DPP with AdjustRBs meets the GFBR requirement for both bandwidths. However, with Postponing and Dropping methods, when the capacity is insufficient (from 2Gbps onwards in Figure 4.a), the gNB fails to transmit packets since the scheduling allocates all resources first, and these methods later check whether they fit. As a result, throughput becomes nearly zero when the allocated

resources exceed the available FH capacity. In contrast, OptimizeRBs allows transmission at restrictive FH capacities but limits the number of RBs per UE without considering the GFBR requirement, which reduces transmission opportunities and results in lower throughput compared to AdjustRBs. Furthermore, Figure 4.b highlights the importance of bandwidth dimensioning according to FH capacity. For example, AdjustRBs and OptimizeRBs deliver the same throughput regardless of whether the bandwidth is 400 MHz or 100 MHz. Interestingly, a larger bandwidth can sometimes be disadvantageous, as a larger Transport Block Size (TBS) with 400 MHz may exceed the FH capacity, reducing the throughput, whereas the 100 MHz bandwidth may avoid this issue.

Figure 5 shows box plots representing the experienced latency when using DPP for a capacity equal to 2Gbps and 700Mbps. The lower and upper edges of the box correspond to the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. Besides, the whiskers indicate 1.5 times the Inter Quartile Range (IQR), which represent approximately the 2 and 98 percentiles. Outliers are represented by circles corresponding to values that exceed the mentioned percentiles. As shown in Figure 5.a, DPP is able to stabilize the queues without saturating the system, and the latencies obtained with the Dropping, Postponing, and AdjustRBs fronthaul control methods for the 75th percentile of packets are lower than 3ms for both applications. This evinces that the FH capacity is not limiting the system when the DPP scheduler is used. In contrast, since OptimizeRBs modifies the radio resource allocation done by the DPP scheduling scheme, the figure shows that the experienced latency increases. When the FH capacity decreases (Figure 5.b), and as was previously observed in Figure 4.b, Dropping and Postponing methods are unable to allow any packet transmission, resulting in zero latency. Meanwhile, AdjustRBs increases the latency because DPP can no longer stabilize the queues and meet the necessary GFBR for each application. However, latencies obtained with AdjustRBs remain lower than those with OptimizeRBs.

Fig. 5. Obtained latency with DPP scheduler when the FH capacity is equal to a) 2Gbps and b) 700Mbps.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have defined, implemented and evaluated a new fronthaul capacity-aware control method tailored for functional split option 7.2x, and designed for effective integration with different MAC scheduling schemes. Among the evaluated fronthaul control techniques, the proposed AdjustRBs method is the only one that does not alter the allocation of radio resources by the MAC scheduler, while considering the maximum capacity that the fronthaul can manage during the allocation process. In addition, when the fronthaul capacity is very restrictive, AdjustRBs is the only method that can maintain acceptable network performance. The results indicate that when the MAC scheduler is focused on meeting QoS requirements, as it is the case with DPP and QoS schedulers, it is more effective not to modify its behavior which is the main objective of AdjustRBs fronthaul control method, allowing to maximize the QoS requirements fulfillment. In our future work, we will extend the fronthaul control methods to other splits, such as functional split option 4, where the MAC is not centralized and packet dropping or postponing is done at the RLC layer. Furthermore, further work could consider more complex RAN scenarios, in terms of multiple cells and radio units, and various fronthaul network architectures, including shared fronthaul scenarios.

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REFERENCES

- [1] 3GPP TSG RAN, "Study on new radio access technology: Radio access architecture and interfaces," Rel. 14, TR 38.801, v14.0.0, 2017.
- [2] O-RAN Working Group 6, *Cloud Architecture and Deployment Scenarios for O-RAN Virtualized RAN*, 2023.
- [3] S. Lagín, *et al.*, "Fronthaul-aware Scheduling Strategies for Dynamic Modulation Compression in Next Generation RANs," in *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 2725-2740, 2023.
- [4] K. Koutlia, *et al.*, "System Analysis of QoS Schedulers for XR Traffic in 5G NR," in *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, vol. 125, pp. 102745, 2023.
- [5] N. Villegas-Saiz, *et al.*, "Extending QoS-aware Scheduling in ns-3 5G-LENA: A Lyapunov based Solution," in *Proc. of the Workshop on ns-3 (WNS'24)*, Castelldefels, Barcelona, 2024, pp. 54-59.
- [6] 3GPP TSG RAN WG1 107-e, "Performance evaluation results for XR," R1-2111046, e-Meeting, 2021.
- [7] Jordi Pérez-Romero, *et al.*, "A Tutorial on the Characterisation and Modelling of Low Layer Functional Splits for Flexible Radio Access Networks in 5G and Beyond," in *IEEE Comm. Surv. & Tut.*, vol. 25, pp. 2791-2833, 2023.
- [8] 3GPP TSG RAN WG3, "CU-DU split: Refinement for Annex A (Transport network and RAN internal functional split)," R3-162102, Sophia Antipolis, France, 2016.
- [9] 3GPP TSG RAN, "Study on XR (Extended Reality) evaluations for NR," 3GPP TR 38.838, Rel. 17, v17.0.0, 2022.
- [10] CPRI Specification v7.0, *Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) Interface Specification*, 2015.